

Requirements for Organizing Independent Work of Students and its Levels

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the issues based on analyzing requirements for organizing independent work of students and its levels. Organizing and managing independent work is the responsible and difficult work of every teacher. Fostering activity and independence must be considered as an integral part of the education of students. This task is among the tasks of paramount importance for every teacher. Independent work is not an end in itself. It is a means of fighting for deep and lasting knowledge of students, a means of developing their activity and independence as personality traits, and developing their mental abilities. And, perhaps, the main function of independent work is the formation of a highly cultural personality, because Only through independent intellectual and spiritual activity does a person develop.

Keywords: Independent work, activity, personality, mental abilities, requirements.

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions of the development of science, the rapid accumulation and updating of information, it is impossible to train a person for life, but at the same time it is important to instill in him an interest in accumulating knowledge and teach him to learn. Therefore, the desire to develop students' ability to independently acquire knowledge and quickly adapt to new areas of activity comes to the fore. The student must not only acquire a certain amount of knowledge, but also be able to independently draw conclusions, think creatively, be able to independently replenish their knowledge, and navigate the rapidly growing flow of information.

Success largely depends on the organization of independent work, which helps to increase the effectiveness of learning and has great educational

significance. Independent work fosters the cognitive activity of students, is an important condition for self-organization and self-discipline in mastering the methods of cognitive activity, and develops in students a psychological attitude towards independent systematic replenishment of their knowledge and the development of skills to navigate the flow of various information when solving cognitive problems.

DISCUSSIONS

The desire to independently and creatively master knowledge, to complete tasks that require criticality of the mind, imagination, fantasy, and dreams - these are the indispensable conditions for the emergence of deep interest in academic subjects. Independent work is considered as a specific form of student's educational activity, characterized by all its features. This is a form of self-education related to the student's educational activities. The concept of independent work of a student in modern didactics necessarily correlates with the organizing role of the teacher.

Independent work refers to various types of individual and collective activities of students, carried out by them in class and extracurricular activities or at home on assignments without the direct participation of the teacher. The general pedagogical definition of extracurricular and extracurricular work, according to which it represents various types of educational and educational activities of students, organized and conducted by the school during extracurricular hours, forms the basis for considering the independent activities of students.

Progressive teachers have always believed that in the classroom students should work as independently as possible, and the teacher should guide this independent work and provide material for it. Experts in this field emphasized that it is important to give students a method, a guiding thread for organizing the acquisition of knowledge, and this means equipping them with the skills and

abilities of the scientific organization of mental work, i.e. the ability to set a goal, choose the means to achieve it, and plan work over time.

Currently, there are several approaches to revealing the essence of the concept of independent work. According to various researchers, independent work is: a form of learning (N.G. Dairi, I.I. Ilyasov, etc.); teaching method (A.V. Usova); type of educational activity (R.B. Sroda, O.A. Nilson); a means of organizing and managing cognitive activity (P.I. Pidkasisty, E.L. Belkin).

The definition given by B.P. is most actively used in didactics. Esipov - independent work of students included in the learning process is such work that is performed without the direct participation of the teacher, according to his instructions, at a time specially provided for this, while students consciously strive to achieve the goal set in the task, showing their efforts and expressing their in one form or another the results of one's mental or physical (or both) actions.

B.P. Esipov identifies the following as the main features of independent work:

- students' activities without outside help;
- availability of a task;
- lack of direct teacher intervention;
- specially allotted time for completing the task;
- presentation of results in one form or another.

P.I. Pidkasisty, while researching this problem, notes that the definition of independent work should reflect the student's creativity and the unity of the procedural and logical-content aspects of independent activity. They, according to Pidkasisty, are not sufficiently taken into account in educational practice, giving rise to boring and monotonous activities of the student. He believes that independent work is a means that, in each specific learning situation, corresponds to a specific goal and task.

I.T. Ogorodnikov, justifying the need for independent work, recommended the following types of combination of teacher activities and student activities, which have not lost their relevance today:

- the teacher himself does not present the material, but only organizes the independent work of students to study it;
- learning new material begins with student reports;
- the teacher dwells only on the main issues, and students study secondary material independently;
- the teacher gives only an introduction to the topic, and students, under his guidance, independently study all the material.

He rightly pointed out that the main, fundamental role of the teacher is to encourage students to independent logical thinking, teach them analysis, determination of cognitive tasks and problems of the lesson, application of acquired knowledge and acquired educational skills, including practical ones.

MATERIALS AND ANALYSIS

Analyzing all possible approaches, we can take the following definition as a basis: independent work is a type of educational activity in which students, under the guidance of a teacher and without his direct participation, perform individual, group and frontal tasks, making mental and physical efforts for this and demonstrating self-control and self-correction.

The main features of students' independent work include the following:

1. external signs of students' independence in completing tasks are the ability to plan their work, complete tasks without the direct help of a teacher and evaluate the result of their work;
2. systematic implementation by students of self-monitoring of the results of their work, adjustment and improvement of methods of its implementation;
3. the presence of a cognitive task, a problematic situation that encourages students to engage in independent intellectual activity;

4. students' manifestation of independence and creative activity in solving the cognitive tasks assigned to them;

5. inclusion in tasks for independent work of material, the assimilation of which would contribute to the holistic development of the student's personality, self-education and creativity.

The effectiveness of independent work depends on its organization, skillful thinking and combination of independent work with other types of work in foreign language lessons.

The rational organization of independent work in foreign language lessons is determined by the measure of the student's readiness for this type of activity. In methodological science, there are different types of readiness:

- motivational readiness (it is determined by the students' interest in learning a foreign language);
- intellectual readiness (it presupposes a certain level of formation of basic mental processes);
- linguistic readiness (proficiency in certain lexical and grammatical material);
- communicative readiness (ability to engage in communication);
- readiness for conscious and rational self-organization (explanation by the teacher of the goals and objectives of each specific type of independent work).

• When developing plans for individual independent work in foreign language lessons, the following conditions must be observed:

1. Taking into account the degree of complexity of educational material.
2. Attitude of students to the subject.
3. Correlation of the proposed task for independent work with the student's overall workload in other subjects in the appropriate period of time.
4. Taking into account the level of performance and health of the student, avoiding additional overload of students.

5. Taking into account the level of development of students' skills in independent work in a foreign language.

6. Reliance in organizing independent work on help from parents and other students.

Organizing independent work in foreign language lessons requires a lot of preliminary work. This preliminary work involves:

- formation of skills and abilities to work with a textbook, reading book, reference books (grammatical, regional studies), various types of dictionaries, special instructions, and technical teaching aids;
- developing students' skills in rationally completing homework and planning their educational activities;
- instructing students on the procedure for completing tasks for independent work and drawing up a report on their completion;
- determination of methods for providing prompt assistance to students when performing independent work;
- operational monitoring of the progress of independent work and identification of typical errors and difficulties;
- encouragement and stimulation of students who successfully complete independent tasks.

In various lessons, through various types of independent work, students can acquire knowledge, skills and abilities. All this work only gives positive results when it is organized in a certain way and meets certain requirements.

When organizing independent work, attention should be paid to the following didactic requirements:

- Independent work should contribute to the solution of basic didactic tasks - the acquisition by students of deep and lasting knowledge, the development of their cognitive abilities, the formation of the ability to independently acquire, expand and deepen knowledge, and apply it in practice.

- Independent work must satisfy the basic principles of didactics, and, above all, the principles of accessibility and systematicity, the connection of theory with practice, conscious and creative activity.

- The work and exercises included in the system should be varied in educational purpose and content to ensure that students develop a variety of skills and abilities.

- The sequence of homework and class work should logically follow from previous independent work and prepare the ground for subsequent work. In this case, not only “short-range” but also “long-distance” connections are provided between individual jobs. The success of solving this problem depends not only on the teacher’s pedagogical skills, but also on how he understands the meaning and place of each individual work in the system of work, in the development of students’ cognitive abilities, their thinking and other qualities.

However, following the requirements alone does not determine the success of the teacher’s work in developing knowledge, skills and abilities in students. To do this, you also need to know the basic principles, guided by which you can ensure the effectiveness of independent work, as well as the methodology for guiding certain types of independent work. When selecting types of independent work, when determining its volume and content, one should be guided, as in the entire learning process, by the basic principles of didactics. The most important in this matter are the principle of accessibility and systematicity, the connection between theory and practice, the principle of gradual increase in difficulties, the principle of creative activity, as well as the principle of a differentiated approach to students. The application of these principles to the management of independent work will greatly facilitate the selection of the desired type of independent work, facilitate its organization and subsequent implementation.

Zharova L.V. examines independent work from an organizational point of view, and highlights:

- existence of a goal of independent work;
- presence of a specific task;
- clear definition of the form of expression of the result (oral, written, practical);
- determining the form for checking the results of independent work;
- the obligation to complete the work by each student who receives the task.

CONCLUSION

Research by practicing scientists and psychologists allows us to conditionally identify four levels of independent activity of students, corresponding to their learning capabilities:

1. Copying actions of students according to a given pattern. Identification of objects and phenomena, their recognition by comparison with a known sample. At this level, students are prepared for independent activity.

2. Reproductive activity to reproduce information about various properties of the object being studied, generally not going beyond the level of memory. However, at this level the generalization of techniques and methods of cognitive activity begins, their transfer to solving more complex but typical problems.

3. Productive activity of independent application of acquired knowledge to solve problems that go beyond the boundaries of a known sample, requiring the ability to make inductive and deductive conclusions.

4. Independent activity to transfer knowledge when solving problems in completely new situations, conditions for drawing up new decision-making programs, developing hypothetical analogue thinking.

CONCLUSION

To improve the quality of education, the development of students' cognitive enthusiasm and interest in the subject is of particular importance. Students must understand the purpose of studying the proposed material. Moreover, modern students have the right to want their learning activities to be interesting and

satisfying. Each of these levels, although they are identified conditionally, exists objectively. Giving an independent task to a student at a higher level is, at best, a waste of time during the lesson.

Naturally, the maximum program for any creative teacher is to bring as many students as possible to the fourth level of independence. However, it should be remembered that the path to it lies only through the three previous levels. Accordingly, a program of actions for the teacher is built when organizing independent work in the lesson.

It follows that it is possible to improve not only the quality of organizing and conducting independent work of future teachers, but also to make it easier for the students themselves by observing simple requirements for it and enhance their language competence.

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